

PHARMACOGENETICS AND MEDICAL-CLINICAL- PHARMACEUTICAL ETHICS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issues of pharmacogenetics and medical-clinical-pharmaceutical ethics. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it discusses, at a broad and in-depth level, a topic that permeates the technical training of students in the areas of health sciences, pharmaceutical sciences and medical sciences, revealing its interdisciplinary nature. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it informs the general public about the possibilities of treatments that may be available in a relatively short time, if the government is interested in investing in such ventures. This is an integrative bibliographical research, of an intervening nature, based on authors who are researching the subject and its ethical and bioethical dimensions. If these studies were undertaken, they would improve the living conditions and health of the population, through the increase in the clinical knowledge of doctors and in the performance of pharmacists in their practice. The conclusions reached are that pharmacogenetics, empirically, is already present in the daily lives of clinical pharmacists, who, upon detecting the resistance of a certain pathogen to a pharmacological compound, immediately associate, by deduction and technical knowledge, that all medications belonging to that pharmacological class may have no effect. In the same way, if a patient complains that the drug has had no effect on his or her organism, he or she already deduces that there is a genetic incompatibility between the two, making it necessary to seek a different chemical formula, which may even be just the vehicle used in the composition and not necessarily the active ingredient of the pharmacochemical compound.

Keywords: Pharmacogenetics. Pharmacogenomics. Ethics. Bioethics.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific development of medical and pharmaceutical sciences, with the discovery of new treatments through new drugs with greater potential for efficiency against pathogenic agents, represented an unprecedented clinical-biochemical advance in history; however, as a

consequence of studies arising from the responses and interpretation of the behavior of patients, pathogens, and molecules, a deeper step in understanding the process was taken: the analysis of gene behavior, and it was understood that environmental, ethnic, and nutritional factors can significantly interfere with the results of treatments applied to different patient groups.

In this sense, the idea arose of associating the patient's genetic compatibility with the gene of the protein being used as a drug, where such action could be responsible for synergistic or antagonistic effects in the organism, potentially causing anything from simple adverse reactions to extreme cases of intoxication, anaphylactic shock, and, consequently, death. Thus, the proposal for the development of pharmacogenetics was linked to ensuring patient safety and medical practice in the treatment of simple and/or serious illnesses.

Proportionally, the opportunity arose to analyze the genetic structure of pathogenic agents and, based on this analysis, develop drugs that directly attack protein chains, breaking them and rendering their direct action on individuals ineffective. This would, in fact, considerably reduce the duration and effectiveness of treatment. Knowledge of the compatibility of the genes of both agents has allowed for considerable advances in solving problems that were previously considered difficult to solve and, in some cases, even unsolvable.

When analyzing the issue from the perspective of medical advancement and the safety it would represent for both patients and doctors, one is faced with a question that is beyond dispute; however, when considering *the* overall sociological condition in which the majority of the population lives in relative poverty regarding access to basic consumer goods and healthcare, whom would this type of medical-pharmaceutical-biochemical service actually serve?

pharmacogenetics cannot be considered the *magnum opus* of Medicine, because if it depends on an analytical DNA and RNA test to determine the genetic compatibility between the patient's gene and that of the drug used, the patient may have already died from poisoning. Thus, we arrive at the first point of ethical divergence, which is that of medical practice, the relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between its theoretical knowledge and its practice, arising from its experience in situations of extreme risk and compassion.

Ethics is a poorly understood term, theoretically and only in the field of empiricism is it understood as what it actually represents, which is behavior; that is, what social treatment is given to the behavior of genes within the scope of biochemistry? This work raises two highly complex questions: the first concerns how the pharmaceutical team will handle the production of data on patients' DNA and RNA; who will train them, or will this knowledge remain restricted to a few scholars in specific areas? What will become of the results of biogenetic and

pharmacogenetic tests ? Could this be used to create a form of postmodern eugenics, in which there would be a database and private information to be traded, according to clients' paychecks, life insurance companies, *holding companies* ?

This work is justified by the sociological dimension that the subject exposes, at a moment in human history where issues such as social exclusion of all kinds, eugenics, nutrition, and access to goods and services demand that advances in the fields of medical and pharmaceutical sciences encompass everyone under the precept of protecting and guaranteeing the full and unrestricted right to the dignity of the human person.

The general objective of this work is to understand how pharmacogenetics can contribute to improving clinical-medical-pharmaceutical-biochemical care, thus reducing cases of contamination and/or drug poisoning, especially in cases of hospital admission and when dealing with severe and highly serious diseases and/or high pathogenic complexity. Specific objectives include understanding the pharmacist's role in the analysis and determination of pharmacology based on pharmacogenetic interpretation , and understanding the pharmacist's responsibility in handling personal data regarding the biogenetic structure of patients undergoing treatment through pharmacogenetics .

ABOUT PHARMACOGENETICS AND PHARMACOGENOMICS

Discoveries through genome decoding research have advanced our understanding of how genes can be compatible or incompatible, especially with regard to proteins used for pharmacological purposes, clarifying synergistic and antagonistic actions in organisms. With this, the advancement of genomic sciences has allowed the creation of such a revolutionary therapeutic option that, if proven and accepted, it will completely change the concept of drug prescription in Medicine (Sadée , 1999), representing a true revolution in the field of Medicine as we know it today, and in the fields of Biochemistry and clinical pharmacology.

Azevêdo (2005) argues that, from the pharmaceutical industry's point of view, the large-scale application of pharmacogenomics could reduce the costs of producing a new molecule for medicinal purposes by up to 60%. Enthusiasts extol the advantages of using the right drug, for the right person, at the right dose. This new chapter in medical practice is being called *personalized medicine* , in contrast to traditional medicine, already dubbed by some as "*one size fits all* ," that is, in a derogatory reference to medication for everyone's use, without distinction based on *precision* obtained through a technical examination.

It must be clarified that such analysis will not guarantee the much-touted and desired precision; it will only considerably reduce the chances of medical errors in prescribing medications. Despite all the enthusiasm from the pharmaceutical industry, pharmacogenomics, like so many other advances in medicine, is immersed in ethical questions, especially in developing countries.

Furthermore, it should be added that the human being is not a homogeneous organism, and each population possesses particularities and singularities that may not be adequately addressed by a mechanical examination. Once again, it is up to medical expertise, knowledge, and experience to attend to and resolve omitted cases, which may be related to geography, the patient's emotional state, their ethnicity, and nutritional history; data that are found through a well-elaborated and well-directed anamnesis.

For didactic purposes, it must be said that,

Pharmacogenomics is the science that studies the interaction between genes and drugs, where through the analysis of specific regions of DNA it is possible to obtain information about the patient's metabolization profile for a given drug, as well as the expected response to treatment. Therefore, pharmacogenomics aims to reduce the occurrence of adverse drug effects, thus identifying a better way to adhere to the chosen pharmacotherapy, adjusting concentrations, and thereby reducing the risks involved (Santana, Conceição and Oliveira, 2022, p. 2).

It represents an unprecedented advance and great possibilities for improving healthcare services and living conditions for the population; however, what percentage of the population would have access to this type of intervention? It seems like just a rhetorical question; however, the question to be asked is, what diseases would imply the application of a treatment of such magnitude, requiring such a deep and delicate invasion of the human body?

For clarification, these are diseases considered rare and about which there is still not much knowledge, precisely because they are not common among individuals. Therefore, how will they be able to identify transformations and variations through more detailed genomic analysis? What materials will they compare to determine if they are on the right track in developing a therapy that can actually prove effective against the pathological agent under study?

These are issues that must be taken into account when making decisions about investments in these fields, considering that there are other, simpler diseases that, due to their recurrence and high incidence, cause much more significant impacts on the population, their health, and living conditions. Decisions to promote medical and scientific advances are always commendable and worthy of any undertaking; however, when considering the resulting benefits

and the scope of their real effect, ethical questions arise that go far beyond the trivial matter of knowing how the genetic material extracted from patients and similar issues will be used.

Many ideas are produced and reported randomly, without considering the details of each operation and the object of study in question, as if scientists actually believed that every human organism responds in a synchronized way to all phenomenological categories, regardless of endogenous and exogenous situations. It's possible that the general population, due to their limited knowledge of medicine and its variations, may also believe in such things and endorse revelations about innovative discoveries in this field. However, it is not possible to have found objective answers that allow for a decisive line of reasoning regarding the behavior of the human organism in response to the action of pathogenic agents, and thus create a medicine that acts intelligently and precisely in combating the ills caused by them.

A discovery of this magnitude would represent a major medical advance; but would it have the same significance in the social field? Each patient would have to undergo rigorous genomic and pharmacogenomic testing, followed by the determination of dosages for each case, and what would be the impact on the pharmaceutical industry, having to prepare exclusive doses for a single patient? These are general questions that, despite being mere speculations, are just as likely as the possibility of such procedures becoming a widespread reality outside the confines of research laboratories.

Adding to the discussion is the problem that...

Individual responses to medications or drugs vary, and much of this variability is due to genetic or hereditary factors. Pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics address the influence of genetic factors on drug response. Pharmacogenetics [*specifically*] has as its greatest promise contributing to the individualization of therapy, that is, prescribing the right medication, at the appropriate dose for each individual, based on knowledge of the genetic factors that modulate the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of medications (Silva and Andrade, 2007, p. 2).

The industrial-scale production of pharmaceuticals follows a generic pattern, coupled with attempts to reduce costs and make them accessible to the largest possible number of individuals. However, when considering the creation of drugs targeted at specific problems and with equally effective results, one faces an *almost* insurmountable challenge given the technical limitations and knowledge of the etiopathogenesis of most complex human diseases.

The synchronization between the protein biological agents of drugs and those of the human organism to reach a level of equilibrium is a game of intentions that is not believed to be achievable even through probabilistic methods; at most, one can approach a condition of interpretation and a possibility of obtaining agents to combat pathogeneses without causing

greater damage to the patients' immune system. Even with all the advances in research and the knowledge acquired, it is clear that it is still not enough to understand the mechanisms of the human body and determine anything definitively.

In the meantime, a philosophical element is introduced, highlighting ethics and, more specifically, bioethics, because both will propose profound discussions and arguments about medications and their production methods, as well as the use of information derived from interventions on patients, even regarding the potential for encompassing this condition considered by many to be revolutionary. However, this expression becomes a euphemism when one considers a revolution that neither changes anyone's life nor allows for new perspectives on solutions to the ills that afflict the population.

Possibly, the dissemination of knowledge acquired throughout the research, even if it proves to be mere hypothesis, would help those who work directly in patient care, so that at the slightest sign of suspected incompatibility, observed empirically through the reaction to medications, it would provide an adequate level of safety to users of medical-pharmacological services, because they would already seek to offer a new class of antibiotics, thus avoiding risks of resistance and/or delays and even failures in the healing processes.

A multitude of results and improvements in the care of patients sensitive to certain classes of antibiotics would ensure agility in clinical procedures, minimizing margins and possibilities of error, thereby reducing direct and indirect costs, and even situations that pose a risk of death. Knowing that such investments are largely public funds, what governments could create is a database that is open for consultation, allowing health science students to access it from the beginning of their academic training. This would result in a more solid and powerful professional development, based on a broader knowledge base in the fields of pharmacology combined with genetics and genomics.

The general idea that the possibilities for applying pharmacogenetics / pharmacogenomics are broad and also include the identification of new therapeutic targets, the optimization of clinical pharmacology protocols, the development of genetic tests for drug selection, and the revision of dosage regimens (Silva and Andrade, 2007) cannot be disregarded. It is important to emphasize that its widespread use cannot become a refuge for medical incompetence, clarifying that it becomes an additional tool in medical and pharmaceutical care, where...

At the time of administering a medication, the ideal approach would be to perform assessments of absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion, according to the pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic parameters of the

drug in question. However, this type of procedure is obviously impractical to perform at the beginning of each treatment and for the general population (Silva and Andrade, 2007, p. 2).

It is worth reiterating what has already been discussed above, in which the expertise and analytical-synthetic capacity of the physician continues to prove essential for well-directed treatment and a broad expectation of cure. By extension, the correct guidance from the pharmacist regarding the use of the drug and its expected response cycles by the body is crucial, enabling the patient to know what to seek in case of delays in their therapeutic drug recovery.

The author, cited above, explains that, immediately, until the medications complete an organic cycle, no type of intervention can be directed because there has not been time to determine whether or not there is *pharmacogenetic* incompatibility. This becomes an ethical issue, since, without knowledge of how the treatments work, it will be up to medical expertise to explain the process to the patient and allow time for an adequate response.

This situation leads to another, more complex one, in which the patient must be aware of everything they are undergoing, including the probabilities of success and failure. They cannot be misled by false expectations of cure and/or improvements in their health, especially if the treatment they are undergoing is experimental, leaving them free to accept or not. It is always necessary to clarify that no science is governed by exactness in its scientific results. The most that can be achieved is to approach more effective results as the behavior of pathogenic agents becomes better understood, in the case of medical and pharmaceutical sciences. This is a complex game because numerous variables come into play as progress is made; that is, the more one knows about the psychology of the object, paradoxically, the more the range of questions expands, not the range of objective, clarifying answers.

The human organism is very complex, and the relationships that have generated changes in DNA structures, however subtle they may be considered, have been sufficient to create modifications such as resistance and vulnerabilities to a multitude of pathologies and pathogens. It is not possible to obtain a study, even in the 21st century, that can representatively answer the challenges of modern medicine. Adequate and transparent information, accessibility to medication, and changes in lifestyle habits are the safest steps towards a healthy life, avoiding self-medication. When clinical care and medication are necessary, the probability of their effectiveness is much higher, leaving rare cases of genetic incompatibility and cases of intoxication/ allergy to be analyzed according to the clinical and symptomatic manifestation.

Pilla, Amorozo, and Furlan (2006) argue that lack of information and difficulty in accessing appropriate medication are the factors that most compromise health. However, in the

patient-medication relationship, we find the pharmacist as the technical manager of establishments that conduct research, produce, distribute, market, and manage the entire process related to this product. Among the work tools used by this professional in pharmacies and drugstores is *Pharmaceutical Care*, which, considering the professional-user relationship, provides guidance on the safety and efficacy of the medication, is responsible for monitoring the drug treatment, "as well as deserving special attention to health promotion, in the prevention of the inappropriate use of this medication" (OLIVEIRA, 2015, p. 145).

The author further clarifies that this direct contact between individuals involves values, principles, anxieties, motivations, social and cultural aspects, power relations, among other equally important factors. Relevant aspects such as individual and social responsibility, vulnerability, confidentiality, and discrimination, within a broader range of concepts, should certainly be taken into account when evaluating the results achieved through the adopted drug therapy (OLIVEIRA, 2015).

This approach seeks to develop patient-centered care through sensitive listening, analyzing everything from the presented symptoms to expectations regarding prescribed medications and trust in the professional. Psychological and psychosomatic factors can influence organic responses to drug treatments. Through pharmacogenetic screening, this issue could be clarified satisfactorily and accurately; however, the purchasing power of both citizens and healthcare centers, which lack materials and specialized personnel with knowledge and mastery of the techniques, not only hinders but also prevents such actions from being implemented on a large scale. This leaves professionals with empirical knowledge and sensitivity to act following this line of thought.

Pharmacogenetics and its implications

Every scientific discovery, culminating in innovation in the field of health sciences, is marked by ethical dilemmas, precisely because it opens precedents for invasion of the patient's body, which, in accordance with the 1988 Federal Constitution, in its article V, Inc., determines as inviolable the intimacy, private life, honor, and image of individuals (Brazil, 2017). No gene exists without its owner; it is determinant of someone's identity; its recognition leads to a specific agent; and how access to this information will be granted, who will keep it confidential, and what purposes will be put to its use are the emblematic questions involving pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics.

Quite different from what one might argue about these two scientific activities in the field of pharmaceutical sciences, where their categorization as commercial products, where only wealthy individuals could have access to treatments under this direction, this thinking shows the sociological immaturity of the analysts and, in the same proportion, claiming that the pharmaceutical industry would save billions a year in the development of new molecules is another naiveté in the sense of recognizing what the animal organism and its behavior are, since genomic research has revealed that the differences in human DNA between individuals are only 3%, which is enough to have so many different personalities and aesthetics.

Another detail is the ethnic diversity of populations like the Brazilians, for example, where etiopathogenic situations present themselves in diverse ways, preventing doctors from making generic diagnoses, as occurs with some pathologies in countries like the United States of America. A more complex situation is the logistics of laboratories equipped with such analytical and interpretive instruments; the transport time and the time to carry out the comparative study could mean the difference between life and death for the patient in an emergency situation. Therefore, the issue is not simply which segment of the population would have access to this resource, but what difference it would make to have it available to society, given that it represents a substantial investment with a negligible potential return on investment.

Based on this, it follows that research should be funded by the State, by the Public Authorities, because the amounts invested directly and the time required to arrive at plausible results are too long, and are not in the interest of private initiative. This is an ethical issue, because once the State has financed all the investigative work, it has the right to have the results made available to the entire population, without restriction, through open information databases accessible to anyone who wishes to consult them.

As already discussed, the presence of a particular protein or enzyme at adequate activity levels to meet the *sui generis requirements* of a personalized medication may not be observed due to phenomenological factors such as cultural, social and ethnic differences resulting from the diversity in the quality and/or quantity of food in use, as well as genetic diversity between groups and populations, a situation that is expressed very broadly in Brazil, for example (Azevêdo, 2004).

At one point, the aforementioned author addresses the issue of epigenetics, and this phenomenon is expressed and enhanced by very peculiar environmental conditions, which does not guarantee the effectiveness of genomic testing, since epigenetic manifestations trigger

behavioral changes, a change in protein chains in response to a stress factor, not a direct change in DNA.

Although it is believed that the market will produce smart drugs, that is, a type of protein that, in theory, would specifically attack the pathogenic agent without causing major damage to the rest of the organism, the pharmaceutical industry's interest is focused on making money; therefore, rare diseases will continue to be treated as exceptional; at most, some drug may be manipulated specifically for a particular case in which there is interest in advancing scholarly knowledge about it.

Despite advancements in knowledge about diseases, epidemiology determines which diseases deserve greater attention and which will receive the largest volume of financial, technical, and human resources. In cases where a very small portion of the population is affected by a particular illness, substantial investments in terms of time and return on investment are not justified by the direct application of knowledge about the problem. And, however senseless this argument may seem, the limitation of essential resources such as money and time, coupled with the impact of certain diseases on the general population, leads those responsible for administrative decision-making to opt for investing where a broader impact can be achieved, both in terms of the number of individuals directly served and in terms of obtaining a greater and faster return on invested capital.

Another detail here is the dubious guarantee that the result obtained will be as expected. There is still no certainty, beyond that provided by statistics, that the genes will be reliably compatible. All tests available to date are inconclusive, guaranteeing a closer approximation in clarifying how organisms function.

Continuing this argument, Azevedo (2004) poses a provocative question: how can we, and who can, empirically guarantee that drugs developed through pharmacogenomics will not have adverse effects on patients? He concludes with an argumentative question: "If a medical advance, such as pharmacogenomics, will not improve the lives of most people, can it, from an ethical point of view, be considered *progress*?" (p. 147)

The question that arises is whether she is correct; taken from this point of view, what we have as a result can be considered progress from the point of view of increasing scientific knowledge, an exponential rise in the myriad of hypotheses about treatments and possibilities of cure; however, it does not fulfill one of the main premises of science, which is its broad social role.

From a sociological and ethical standpoint, the interest of all development, in any field of scientific knowledge, should be geared towards offering improvements in the living

conditions of the population, both directly and indirectly. When this does not happen, or the promise proves to be far removed from objective reality, it does not justify all the investment made, because it becomes useless when analyzed from a pragmatic perspective. The result, after years of research and substantial investments, is the presentation of a counterpart to the State and society in the form of knowledge that proves useful and capable of solving problems and, if not, at least clarifies the available treatment options and, from there, allows recourse to the mechanisms of action that can provide access to them, whether directly, through private means or through legal action, and even through public health agencies, when possible.

One of the goals of the patient-patient relationship is to clarify what is affecting them. This is achieved initially through anamnesis (medical history) and *subsequently through examinations*, allowing for a greater understanding of the causes and effects of the pathology. It is at this inflection point that the pharmacist has the opportunity to apply all their technical knowledge of pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics. Pharmacodynamics analyzes the mechanism of action of medications in the body, while pharmacokinetics studies how molecules interact, creating synergy and/or antagonism. This demands a range of knowledge encompassing various other sciences and specific, unique situations relevant to each individual.

In the development of medical-pharmaceutical sciences, genomic knowledge of proteins and its consequent application in the production of new molecules has presented itself as an opportunity to improve the lives of individuals; however, this does not exempt professionals from possessing empirical concepts and knowledge that make all the difference in solving everyday problems. The relationship between patient and professional should be as clear as possible, with a feeling of respect and authority between both, especially from the former towards the latter, strictly following the procedures outlined regarding the use of prescribed medication. All of this is part of the consultation which, in addition to seeking a better understanding of the symptoms and promoting a healing process, through this monitoring, the pharmacist and the doctor can gain an understanding of the effectiveness of the medication and the behavior of the pathogenic agent, in many cases deducing whether or not there has been resistance and/or incompatibility with the molecule used in the therapeutic action.

It should be noted that, in the professional-patient relationship, one cannot...

To disregard the regulatory obligations of healthcare professionals and professional ethics, but rather the direct relationship with basic moral principles, which often appear independent, uncorrelated with each other, and not necessarily with a direct hierarchical line in an assessment of importance (Oliveira, 2015, p. 34).

It is the responsibility of healthcare professionals to be honest and transparent with their patients, informing them of treatment possibilities, alternatives, immediate risks and associated consequences, including costs and results already achieved. The issue of pharmacogenomics would in no way be unethical simply because it is expensive and therefore directed at a very restricted elite. The absence of appropriate conduct by the multidisciplinary team would arise if *they promised* a cure to the user.

Associating ethics with product prices and, because of this, limiting broad access to innovation in the health field is a mistake, and this must be clearly explained. Initially, the investment costs to achieve feasible results with sufficient safety levels to propose a treatment are very high, and even then, after application, the patient must be monitored by a multidisciplinary team of medical scientists for a period of time, generating additional costs. Over time, as variables become better understood and intervention mechanisms are developed, the tendency is for costs to become more relative, allowing access to a larger group of individuals.

All of this represents a type of discussion in which one cannot define the cause by the symptom, because advanced studies in the genomic aspect in relation to diseases are not about satisfying a childish desire to know every type of disease, as if it were possible to create an encyclopedia from genetic analyses of traits from viral and bacterial samples and make them compatible with an organism as complex as the human one, which is affected by all fields, such as culture, environment, and other variables that drive changes in its state of being and acting.

All the knowledge acquired through experiences, analysis, and interpretation thereof, only allows human beings to approach an understanding of the behavior and psychology of the objects that cross their path and challenge them. These objects can never be taken as ends in themselves, nor can they be considered as if there is nothing beyond what is presented to them. With the discovery of DNA and all the possibilities that have been explored, the game of probabilities has become more amenable to decoding, while still remaining, in its essence, a *game of bets* based on hypotheses.

This is the turning point in the analysis and interpretation of studies conducted with living beings, where the focus is on cure, life, and the expectation of all of these simultaneously, all concerning the same object. When referring to ethics in healthcare, it's not about respecting limits with respect to the patient; because the patient is the first one who doesn't care, as long as the results meet their desires. The yearning for salvation obscures all reason that should determine socially acceptable behavioral patterns, creating a way of acting that comes to have its own parameters, transforming the patient into a castaway in the face of life and existence,

clinging to any thread of expectation; a schizopathological state that, once combined with the enthusiasm of the medical team, can end in true ethical aberrations, where responsibility for the entire process disappears.

This would bring us back to the problem that,

The ethics of responsibility reflects on the relationship between the agent, their action, and the consequences of these actions; that is, it seeks to understand the agent's responsibility in relation to the consequences of their actions. The relevant characteristic for this approach is that the principle of responsibility is not based on reciprocity, that is, on the traditional idea of duties and rights, where the establishment of certain rights creates corresponding duties, or where the acceptance of certain duties generates rights for others (Ibid., p. 36).

Here the author clarifies what was discussed above. Since there is no promise of a cure on the part of the team, the patient assumes all the risk associated with the treatment, including the costs directly and indirectly linked to it; based on the understanding that the contracted service was provided satisfactorily.

The ease with which the World Wide Web has given individuals access to all kinds of information has led to the creation of epistemic dependencies on ideas taken out of context, distorting the discussion towards a sociological direction that does not broaden opportunities for medical advancements. Discussions, almost always lacking any anthropological perspective, focus entirely on the economic aspect, leaving the field of knowledge and the pursuit of new discoveries completely outside the scope of the arguments.

pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics may not be applicable on a large scale, their medical-biochemical findings, in the hands and minds of bold professionals, could lead to hypotheses and changes in prognoses. Even if one continued to work with the expectation of trial and error, there would be advances in medical deduction and improvements in clinical care. By linking the two pharmaceutical sciences to the principle of exclusion [*of some or many*], *everyone [without any distinction]* is excluded from an opportunity for advancement in clinical care, on the part of the physician and/or clinical pharmacist.

There is a problem that precedes the microeconomic issue, which is the macroeconomic issue. This directly affects the availability of resources for research in these areas, restricting it to developed countries. Subsequently, when the work is completed, the results are published in highly prestigious international journals, to which only public centers have access due to the high cost of subscriptions to such journals and publications. The researchers' eagerness for prestige leads them to not want to publish their findings in freely circulated and open-access

journals, making it the State's responsibility to intervene in this regard and recognize these innovations.

pharmacogenetic knowledge for healthcare professionals. In the future, "however advanced the research in this area may be, the new concepts will only benefit the patient if they first reach the physician, who must be able to know when a genetic test is useful or necessary, and how to interpret the results" (Silva and Andrade, 2007, p. 8).

This is a symbolic issue because medical care is mostly provided in emergency situations, whether treating cases in urgent care services or in cases requiring hospitalization; however, complex consultations do not represent the highest level of healthcare. Therefore, the knowledge acquired through research and advancements in these areas needs to be available to professionals on the front lines, especially since they are the ones who, after immediately resolving critical situations, make referrals to specialists, who in turn will dedicate themselves to a more complex, in-depth, and comprehensive study of the patient and their pathology.

This is an ongoing process that, as it deepens, becomes increasingly prominent due to the volume of information it makes available to healthcare professionals. However, it cannot be confused, under any circumstances, with empirical knowledge, considering the significant distance involved in confirming the data and results, as well as the variances and variables that arise between one situation and another, between one patient and another. Therefore, the acquired epistemic elements cannot be interpreted as facts, but rather as research into social representation. Each society, in particular, will require unique and specific pharmacogenomic and pharmacogenetic analyses because numerous elements condition and differentiate them, depending on the region in which they are located.

Similarly, the development of ethical concepts can only be achieved as knowledge of molecules and their conditions of synergy and genetic antagonism advances. While the bioethical dimension of large-scale pharmacogenomics application is debated, progress has been limited only by the high costs of such projects; however, wealthy countries have viewed these procedures as means to achieve ends with lower financial costs and reduced suffering, also highlighting that...

The search for more effective treatments with fewer medications and adverse effects, or even personalized drugs, is increasing, enabling the growth of personalized medicine, which aims at pharmacotherapy not only to combat the disease but also the genetic variability of each patient. Pharmacogenomics allows for the expansion of the identification of variations in the DNA gene sequence, distinguishing biomarkers that can contribute not only to better adherence to existing therapies but also to the creation of new genetically specific drugs, in addition to contributing to clinical analytical evaluation in

the discovery of disease diagnoses (Santana, Conceição and Oliveira, 2022, p. 5).

Once more extensive studies are carried out, clinical-medical knowledge at the field level could increase exponentially, allowing for prognoses that more closely match the facts and symptoms reported by patients and more precise indications regarding more complex interventions. The cited authors highlight that advances in clinical studies and pharmacogenetics trials, along with the discovery of genetic mapping, have allowed its application in clinical practice and thus its evolution into pharmacogenomics, defined as the study of the expression of individual genes relevant to disease susceptibility, as well as drug response at the cellular, tissue, individual, or population level. This pharmaceutical-biochemical approach is used to provide precision pharmacotherapy using genomics; it can therefore be used to help select the best medication or assist in dosage. Pharmacogenetics aims to identify the genetic biomarkers responsible for the interaction of drugs with each individual (Santana, Conceição and Oliveira, 2022).

Taking ethics as the science of behavior, the aim of this discussion is to explore the possibilities of improving clinical-medical and pharmaceutical care based on knowledge gained from research conducted through pharmaceutical sciences, particularly pharmacokinetics and pharmacogenomics. Innovative discoveries in the fields of health and medicine, and the interaction between them, present a challenging situation because this knowledge could potentially accelerate healing processes and even avoid the infamous wasted time spent trying to find the appropriate treatment for each particular case.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Studies on pharmacogenetics and ethics reveal a significant interdisciplinary relationship between the health sciences and between healthcare professionals and users. Understanding the pathogenic and genetic factors associated with professional ethics has become extremely important in modern medicine, where rights and duties must be respected in any care. On the one hand, the patient has the right to respectful care, and on the other, they have the duty to be honest about the symptoms that represent the causal link with the diseases the doctor is treating, as well as pharmaceutical care, in which the indicated dosage, combined with an observation of the class of medications to be used, avoids allergenic effects and intoxication, adverse reactions, among other situations that, through conventional methods, are

impossible to predict until they have occurred, in which case medical-pharmaceutical expertise is required.

Each individual reacts uniquely to different drugs, making a thorough understanding of pharmacogenetics essential. This field of knowledge not only enriches clinical practice but also underpins ethical decisions that directly impact patient care.

Pharmacogenetics is already present in the daily work of clinical pharmacists, who, upon detecting the resistance of a particular pathogenic agent to a pharmacological compound, immediately associate, through deduction and technical knowledge, that all medications belonging to that pharmacological class may have no effect. Similarly, if a patient complains that a medication had no effect on their body, they deduce that there is a genetic incompatibility between the two, necessitating the search for a different chemical formula, which may even be only the vehicle used in the composition and not necessarily the active ingredient of the pharmacochemical compound.

This article has sought to discuss the ethical dimension linked to the development of research that leads to empirical proof of the use of medications and treatments based on the application of the principles of pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics. Several points need to be addressed and analyzed, ranging from funding for such scientific endeavors to the target audience of the results and how the general population can benefit from such advances in medical-pharmaceutical knowledge.

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